

Synthesis, characterization, and *in silico* studies of new benzohydrazide derivatives targeting EGFR kinase

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Abstract

Targeted therapy has improved the management of non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC); however, resistance and suboptimal responses persist, requiring the development of new epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR)-directed chemotypes. A series of benzohydrazide derivatives (3a–f) was synthesized and characterized using FT-IR, ¹H NMR, and ¹³C NMR. *In silico* ADME profiling predicted high oral absorption for the series and acceptable MW/HBD/HBA ranges; however, the elevated predicted lipophilicity (QPlogPo/w > 5) suggested potential solubility and nonspecific binding risks. Compound 3e had the most balanced size and polarity profile, and compound 3f had the highest predicted permeability. Binding was evaluated against two EGFR kinase conformations (PDB: 1M17, active-like; 4HJO, inactive-like) using /native-ligand redocking, docking/induced-fit docking, Prime MM-GBSA, and 200 ns molecular dynamics simulations, together with three EGFR reference inhibitors and five DUD-E decoys. The docking/MM-GBSA results suggested conformation-dependent binding, with 3d favored in 1M17 and 3f in 4HJO, with recurrent ATP-site contacts. Overall, these compounds represent computationally prioritized EGFR-directed scaffolds for experimental validation rather than confirmed EGFR inhibitors.

Keywords

ADME, benzohydrazides, EGFR, molecular docking, molecular dynamics

Introduction

Lung cancer remains one of the most common causes of cancer-related deaths worldwide, and non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) accounts for most cases (Zappa and Mousa 2016; Bray et al. 2024). Dysregulated signaling via receptor tyrosine kinases (RTKs) is a primary promoter of malignant proliferation and survival, rendering RTK pathways promising targets for mechanism-based therapies (Broekman 2011). The epidermal growth factor recep-

tor (EGFR/ERBB) family, which includes EGFR/ERBB1, ERBB2, ERBB3, and ERBB4, is one of the most important in cancer signaling (Mitsudomi and Yatabe 2010). This is because EGFR signaling intersects with pathways such as Ras/MAPK (Ullah et al. 2022). Small-molecule EGFR tyrosine kinase inhibitors (EGFR-TKIs), such as erlotinib and gefitinib, bind to the ATP-binding site and inhibit kinase signaling, providing clinical benefit in selected patient populations (Bareschino et al. 2007). However, therapeutic responses may be limited in EGFR-wild-type disease and

can be restricted by natural or acquired resistance mechanisms (Passaro et al. 2020; Wang et al. 2022). These challenges continue to inspire the search for alternative EGFR-targeted chemotypes that can offer enhanced binding profiles and act as foundations for optimization (Bareschino et al. 2007; Wang et al. 2022). Hydrazide-containing scaffolds, especially hydrazide-hydrazone hybrids, are well known as flexible frameworks for medicinal chemistry and have been linked to anticancer activity against several targets (Teixeira et al. 2025). Benzohydrazide/hydrazone anticancer derivatives are often limited to simple mono-imine aromatic systems and are frequently assessed against a single EGFR structural state (Teixeira et al. 2025).

Unlike typical mono-imine benzohydrazide/hydrazone designs evaluated in a single EGFR state, this series introduces a nabumetone-based bis-azomethine structure and assesses binding across both active-like (1M17) and inactive-like (4HJO) EGFR conformations to explore conformation-dependent recognition (Al-Suwaidan et al. 2015; Murugappan et al. 2024). In this study, a series of benzohydrazide derivatives (3a–f) was synthesized that incorporate a nabumetone-derived 6-methoxynaphthylbutan-2-ylidene hydrophobic anchor, a 4-aminobenzohydrazide core, and a *para*-aryl Schiff base extension, resulting in a bis-azomethine framework with adjustable electronic and polarity characteristics. Because EGFR adopts many conformational states that can influence ligand binding, binding was evaluated across two EGFR conformations, an active-like state (PDB: 1M17) and an inactive-like state (PDB: 4HJO), consistent with reports that erlotinib can engage multiple EGFR states (Park et al. 2012). Accordingly, the design, synthesis, and structural characterization of compounds 3a–f are reported, and their potential as EGFR-directed leads is assessed using a computational workflow, including *in silico* ADME profiling, molecular docking/induced-fit docking, MM-GBSA binding free-energy estimation, and molecular dynamics simulations, to prioritize candidates for subsequent experimental validation.

Materials and methods

Chemicals and materials

All reagents and commonly used intermediates were obtained from commercial suppliers (Sigma-Aldrich/Merck KGaA, Germany) and used as received without additional purification. The solvents used were of HPLC grade.

Characterization methods

Melting points were determined using the open-capillary method with a Stuart SMP10 electric melting-point apparatus. All FT-IR, ¹H NMR, and ¹³C NMR data reported for compounds 1–3f were obtained in the present study. FT-IR spectra (4000–400 cm⁻¹) were recorded using a Bruker ALPHA II spectrometer with a Platinum ATR (diamond)

accessory (Bruker Optik GmbH). ¹H NMR (500 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (125 MHz) spectra were recorded in DM-SO-d₆ on a Bruker Avance 500 MHz spectrometer.

Chemical synthetic procedures and spectral data

Chemical Synthesis of 4-aminobenzohydrazide (1)

Benzocaine (0.165 g, 1.00 mmol) in 100% hydrazine (8.0 mL) was stirred for 10 min at room temperature and then refluxed for 12 h. After cooling, the mixture was poured onto crushed ice, and the precipitate was filtered, washed with water and then diethyl ether, air-dried, and recrystallized from ethanol to obtain needle-shaped white crystals (Taha et al. 2019). M.P.: 222–224 °C; yield 79%; FT-IR (ν, cm⁻¹): 3421, 3342 (aniline NH₂), 3305, 3226 (N-H, hydrazide -CONH-NH₂), 3032 (Ar C-H), 1627 (amide C = O). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 9.31 (s, 1H, N-H), 7.56 (d, 2H, Ar C-H), 6.55 (d, 2H, Ar C-H), 5.58 (s, 2H, aniline NH₂), 4.33 (s, 2H, hydrazide NH₂). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 167.06 (C = O), 152.00 (C-NH₂), 128.93–113.16 (Ar-C).

Chemical synthesis of 4-amino-N'-(4-(6-methoxynaphthalen-2-yl)butan-2-ylidene) benzohydrazide (2)

Compound 1 (0.300 g, 2.00 mmol) was dissolved in absolute ethanol (10.0 mL). Nabumetone (0.440 g, 2.00 mmol) was added and stirred for 15 min at room temperature, and glacial AcOH (4 drops, cat.) was added. The mixture was then refluxed for 6 h. After cooling, the mixture was poured onto crushed ice, and the precipitate was filtered, washed with water and then diethyl ether, air-dried, and recrystallized from ethanol to obtain an off-white powder (Ubaid et al. 2024). M.P.: 167–171 °C; yield 76%, FT-IR (ν, cm⁻¹): 3399–3324 (NH₂), 3218 (amide N-H), 3042 (Ar C-H), 2964–2850 (aliphatic C-H), 1652 (amide C = O), 1627 (C = N), 1598–1578 (Ar C = C). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 9.96 (s, 1H, CONH), 7.73 (d, 2H, naphthyl Ar-H), 7.67–6.57 (10H, phenyl and naphthyl Ar-H), 5.68 (s, 2H, NH₂), 3.85 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 2.96 (t, 2H, Ar-CH₂), 2.64 (t, 2H, CH₂-C = N), 1.97 (s, 3H, N=C-CH₃). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 157.30 (C = N, naphthyl C-6-O), 157.24 (amide C = O), 152.38 (C-NH₂), 137.03, 133.24, 129.30, 129.08, 128.28, 128.07, 127.14, 126.58, 120.77, 118.92, 112.97, 106.22, 55.58, 32.49, 23.47, 17.00.

General procedure for chemical synthesis of compounds 3a–f (hydrazide derivatives)

Compound 2 (0.360 g, 1.00 mmol) was dissolved in absolute ethanol (8.0 mL) and DMF (2.0 mL). The corresponding *para*-substituted aldehydes (benzaldehyde, 4-chlorobenzaldehyde, 4-nitrobenzaldehyde, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde,

4-methoxybenzaldehyde, and 4-(dimethylamino)benzaldehyde (1.00 mmol) and glacial AcOH (4 drops, cat.) were added. The mixture was stirred for 15 min at room temperature and then refluxed for 6 h. After cooling, the mixture was poured onto crushed ice and neutralized with saturated NaHCO₃ until effervescence ceased. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and then diethyl ether, air-dried, and recrystallized from ethanol (Taha et al. 2019).

Chemical synthesis of 4-((4-(benzylideneamino)-N'-(4-(6-methoxynaphthalen-2-yl)butan-2-ylidene)benzohydrazide) (3a)

White powder, M.P.: 259–263 °C; yield 62%, FT-IR (ν, cm⁻¹): 3168 (N-H of hydrazide), 3053–3026 (Ar C-H), 2846 (aliphatic C-H), 1631 (C = O overlapped with C = N), 1598–1578 (Ar C=C). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 11.88 (s, 1H, CONH), 8.66 (s, 1H, HC = N), 7.98–7.11 (15H, phenyl and naphthyl Ar-H), 3.84 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 2.86 (t, 2H, naphthyl-CH₂), 2.64 (t, 2H, CH₂-C = N), 1.97 (s, 3H, N=C-CH₃). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 163.15 (benzylidene C = N), 162.67 (amide C = O), 154.94 (C = N-NH and naphthyl -C-OCH₃), 148.17 (Ar C-N=C), 136.20, 134.82, 132.39, 130.94, 130.56, 129.39, 129.33, 127.57, 126.31, 121.45, 118.95, 106.20, 55.62, 32.53, 23.90, 17.31.

Chemical synthesis of 4-((4-(chlorobenzylidene)amino)-N'-(4-(6-methoxynaphthalen-2-yl)butan-2-ylidene)benzohydrazide) (3b)

White powder; M.P.: 223–226 °C; yield 47%, FT-IR (ν, cm⁻¹): 3388–3217 (N-H of Hydrazide), 3039 (Ar C-H), 2889 (Aliphatic C-H), 1634 (C = O overlapped with C = N), 1596–1574 (Ar C=C), 600 (aryl C-Cl). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 11.53 (s, 1H, CONH), 8.37 (s, 1H, HC = N), 7.87–7.10 (14H, phenyl and naphthyl Ar-H), 3.84 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 2.88 (t, 2H, naphthyl-CH₂), 2.83 (t, 2H, CH₂-C = N), 2.10 (s, 3H, N=C-CH₃). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 163.52 (benzylidene C = N and amide C = O), 152.84 (C = N-NH and naphthyl -C-OCH₃), 145.05 (Ar C-N=C), 134.54, 134.11, 129.88, 129.34, 128.93, 119.76, 113.10, 106.19, 55.57, 37.10, 29.51, 16.31.

Chemical synthesis of N'-(4-(6-methoxynaphthalen-2-yl)butan-2-ylidene)-4-((4-nitrobenzylidene)amino)benzohydrazide (3c)

Orange powder; M.P.: 271–274 °C; yield 70.8%. FT-IR (ν, cm⁻¹): 3392–3217 (N-H of hydrazide), 1652 (C = O overlapped with C = N), 1603–1573 (Ar C=C), 1513 (NO₂ bending). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 11.80 (s, 1H, CONH), 8.48 (s, 1H, HC = N), 8.25–6.64 (14H, phenyl and naphthyl Ar-H), 3.83 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 2.87 (t, 2H, naphthyl-CH₂), 2.81 (t, 2H, CH₂-C = N), 2.09 (s, 3H, N=C-CH₃). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 163.90 (benzylidene C = N and amide C = O), 157.23 (C = N-NH and naphthyl -C-OCH₃), 153.08 (Ar-C-N = C), 147.97 (C-NO₂), 141.56, 136.70, 133.19, 130.36, 130.12, 129.24, 129.00, 128.12, 128.07, 127.15, 126.29, 124.46, 119.47, 118.92, 113.15, 106.16, 55.53, 30.19, 29.51, 18.97.

Chemical synthesis of 4-((4-(hydroxybenzylidene)amino)-N'-(4-(6-methoxynaphthalen-2-yl)butan-2-ylidene)benzohydrazide (3d)

Off-white powder; M.P.: 248–251 °C; yield 53.7%. FT-IR (ν, cm⁻¹): 3478 (phenolic O-H), 3378–3245 (N-H of hydrazide), 3057–3008 (aromatic C-H), 2960–2840 (aliphatic C-H), 1634 (C = O overlapped with C = N), 1598 (Ar C = C). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 11.30 (s, 1H, CONH), 9.89 (s, 1H, Ar-OH), 8.32 (s, 1H, HC = N), 7.69–6.83 (14H, phenyl and naphthyl Ar-H), 3.84 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 2.88 (t, 2H, naphthyl-CH₂), 2.81 (t, 2H, CH₂-C = N), 2.09 (s, 3H, N = C-CH₃). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 163.36 (benzylidene C = N and amide C = O), 159.56 (C = N-NH), 157.24 (C-OH and naphthyl -C-OCH₃), 152.61 (Ar-C-N = C), 136.72, 133.20, 129.70, 129.26, 129.05, 128.11, 127.16, 126.32, 126.18, 120.23, 116.14, 113.10, 106.19, 55.56, 30.22, 29.52, 19.02.

Chemical synthesis of 4-((4-(methoxybenzylidene)amino)-N'-(4-(6-methoxynaphthalen-2-yl)butan-2-ylidene)benzohydrazide (3e)

Off-white powder; M.P.: 197–202 °C; yield 81.3%. FT-IR (ν, cm⁻¹): 3201, 3175 (N-H of hydrazide), 3031 (aromatic C-H), 1631 (C = O overlapped with C = N), 1599–1574 (Ar C = C). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 11.73 (s, 1H, CONH), 8.42 (s, 1H, HC = N), 7.95–7.03 (14H, phenyl and naphthyl Ar-H), 3.84 (s, 3H, naphthyl-OCH₃), 3.81 (s, 3H, benzyl-OCH₃), 2.89 (t, 2H, naphthyl-CH₂), 2.83 (t, 2H, CH₂-C = N), 2.10 (s, 3H, N=C-CH₃). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 162.70 (benzylidene C-OCH₃), 161.66 (benzylidene C = N), 161.29 (amide C = O), 157.25 (naphthyl -C-OCH₃), 155.16 (C = N-NH), 147.94 (Ar-C-N = C), 136.73, 133.21, 131.26, 129.28, 129.25, 129.15, 129.02, 128.11, 127.44, 127.15, 126.32, 121.36, 118.95, 114.81, 114.75, 106.20, 55.91, 55.57, 30.23, 29.52, 15.05.

Chemical synthesis of 4-((4-(dimethylamino)benzylidene)amino)-N'-(4-(6-methoxynaphthalen-2-yl)butan-2-ylidene)benzohydrazide (3f)

Orange powder; M.P.: 169–173 °C; yield 73.1%. FT-IR (ν, cm⁻¹): 3468, 3332, 3199 (N-H of hydrazide aromatic/aliphatic C-H region), 2891 (aliphatic C-H), 1597–1563 (br, C = N azomethine and Ar C = C and amide C = O), 1527–1509 (amide N-H bend and C-N stretch), 1485–1363 (aromatic C = C and N(CH₃)₂ bending vibrations). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 11.17 (s, 1H, CONH), 8.26 (s, 1H, HC = N), 7.94–6.74 (14H, phenyl and naphthyl Ar-H), 3.84 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 2.95 (s, 6H, N(CH₃)₂), 2.88 (t, 2H, naphthyl-CH₂-), 2.83 (t, 2H, CH₂-C = N), 2.10 (s, 3H, N = C-CH₃). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 163.17 (benzylidene C = N and amide C = O), 157.24 (C = N-NH and naphthyl-C-OCH₃), 152.48 (Ar-C-N = C), 151.74 (Ar-C-N(CH₃)₂), 136.73, 133.21, 129.59, 129.26, 129.02, 128.63, 128.11, 127.16, 126.32, 122.54, 120.43, 113.09, 112.30, 106.20, 55.57, 44.56, 30.23, 29.52, 7.05.

Ligand preparation

All ligands were prepared using LigPrep (Schrödinger Release 2024-3, build 138). Ionization and protonation states were generated using Epik under physiological settings (target pH 7.4 ± 2.0), duplicates were removed, and all relevant ionization/tautomeric states were retained for docking (Shelley et al. 2007).

ADME study

Schrödinger Maestro's QikProp was used to predict ADME-related physicochemical and pharmacokinetic descriptors, and the results were exported to Excel for analysis. The evaluated descriptors were organized into two groups. The first group covered drug-likeness and physicochemical profiles, including molecular weight (MW), hydrogen-bond acceptors (HBAs), hydrogen-bond donors (HBDs), QPlog-Po/w, rotatable bonds, human oral absorption, molecular volume, polar surface area (PSA), dipole moment, and globularity. The second group covered predicted permeability, distribution, binding, and metabolism parameters, including QPPCaco, QPPMDCK, QPlogBB, QPlogKhsa, and the number of predicted metabolic reactions (Moodley et al. 2022; Xu et al. 2022). These QikProp data were used to compare candidates to erlotinib and select compounds with balanced lipophilicity, polarity, permeability, and metabolic profiles for computational evaluation.

Protein preparation (EGFR, PDB: 1M17, and 4HJO)

The Protein Preparation Wizard with OPLS4 in Maestro (Schrödinger 2024-3) was used to prepare the active-like and inactive-like EGFR kinase-domain structures 1M17 and 4HJO. Protonation states were assigned with PROPKA at pH 7.4. Prime rebuilt missing side chains. Only water molecules bridging the pocket (≤ 5.0 Å or ≥ 2 H-bonds) were retained for grid generation and docking. Glide receptor grids were centered on the erlotinib centroid (Sahib and Mahdi 2025).

Docking protocol and MM-GBSA

Molecular docking was performed using Glide XP (Schrödinger Suite 2024-3) for each EGFR conformation with flexible ligand sampling enabled. Native-ligand redocking was first performed for the co-crystallized ligand in both EGFR structures to assess whether the docking protocol could reproduce the experimental binding mode. The redocked poses reproduced the crystallographic orientation with RMSD values of 1.25 Å for 1M17 and 2.59 Å for 4HJO. In addition to the synthesized benzohydrazide derivatives (3a–f), three known EGFR inhibitors (erlotinib, gefitinib, and lapatinib) were included as positive reference ligands, while five DUD-E property-matched decoys were included as putative negative controls. All ligands were processed using the same LigPrep, docking, induced-fit docking (IFD), and Prime MM-GBSA workflow.

For each ligand, the top chemically reasonable XP pose was selected based on the docking score, absence of severe steric clashes, and preservation of the expected ATP-site hinge interaction, particularly with MET769. IFD (Glide + Prime) was then carried out on the selected XP poses to allow local receptor adaptation, and the resulting complexes were ranked by IFD score (Cheremnykh et al. 2023). Prime MM-GBSA calculations were subsequently performed on the top complexes using OPLS4 and VSGB 2.1, with more negative ΔG_{bind} values interpreted as more favorable modeled complex energies (Bansal et al. 2024; Kalath et al. 2024). These values were treated as relative estimates for the modeled complexes rather than absolute binding free energies in solution. Therefore, docking, IFD, and MM-GBSA were used only as relative *in silico* tools for prioritizing compounds within the present series.

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulation

The best Glide XP/IFD poses for each EGFR structure (1M17, active-like; 4HJO, inactive-like) produced protein-ligand complexes. Systems were built using Desmond (Schrödinger Suite 2024-3) and the OPLS4 force field. The complexes were solvated in an orthorhombic box using TIP3P water and a 13 Å buffer, then neutralized and ionized to 0.15 M NaCl. Restrained NVT heating to 300 K was followed by NPT equilibration at 1 atm. Each receptor state was simulated for 200 ns. Energies and coordinates were recorded every 1.2 ps and 10 ps, respectively. Trajectory analysis examined protein Ca RMSD/RMSE, ligand heavy-atom RMSD, secondary-structure content, and persistence of key ligand-protein contacts, particularly MET769 (Todsaporn et al. 2023; Ballarotto et al. 2024).

Results

Chemical synthesis

The benzohydrazide derivatives 3a–f were synthesized in three steps from benzocaine, as shown in Fig. 1. In step 1, benzocaine was converted to 4-aminobenzohydrazide (1). In step 2, condensation of compound 1 with nabumetone gave hydrazone 2. In step 3, reaction of compound 2 with the corresponding *para*-substituted aromatic aldehydes afforded the final Schiff base derivatives 3a–f.

In step 1, benzocaine was converted to 4-aminobenzohydrazide (1), confirmed by FT-IR appearance of NH_2 N-H at $3421/3342$ cm^{-1} , $-\text{CONH}-\text{NH}_2$ N-H at $3305/3226$ cm^{-1} , and amide C = O at 1627 cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR showed δ 9.31 (NH) with δ 5.58 (NH_2) and δ 4.33 ($-\text{CONH}-\text{NH}_2$), while ^{13}C NMR confirmed the hydrazide carbonyl at δ 167.06 and the C- NH_2 carbon at δ 152.00. In step 2, reaction of (1) with nabumetone gave hydrazone (2), marked by disappearance of the terminal hydrazide $-\text{NH}_2$ (FT-IR $3305/3226$ cm^{-1} and ^1H δ 4.33) and appearance of amide N-H at 3218 cm^{-1} and C = N at 1627 cm^{-1} (with C = O at 1652 cm^{-1}). ^1H NMR showed new signals at δ 9.96 (CONH), δ 3.85 (OCH_3), and δ 1.97 ($\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), and ^{13}C

Figure 1. Synthetic scheme of new benzohydrazide derivatives.

NMR showed δ 157.30 (C = N) and δ 157.24 (C = O). In step 3, formation of the final derivatives 3a–f was confirmed by the disappearance of the NH₂ signal of compound 2 and the appearance of the second azomethine linkage. In the FT-IR spectra of 3a–f, the NH₂ band of compound 2 at 3399–3324 cm⁻¹ disappeared, while the conjugated C=N/C=O region appeared within 1597–1652 cm⁻¹ across the series. In the ¹H NMR spectra, the azomethine proton (HC=N) appeared at δ 8.26–8.66, and the hydrazide NH (CONH) appeared at δ 11.17–11.88. In the ¹³C NMR spectra, the benzyldene C=N and amide C=O carbons appeared in the downfield region at approximately δ 161–164. Substituent changes were also observed, including the aryl C-Cl band at 600 cm⁻¹ for 3b, the NO₂ band at 1513 cm⁻¹ and C-NO₂ signal at δ 147.97 for 3c, the phenolic O-H band at 3478 cm⁻¹ and proton at δ 9.89 for 3d, the benzyl-OCH₃ signal at δ 3.81 and carbon at δ 162.70 for 3e, and the N(CH₃)₂ signal at δ 2.95 with the corresponding aromatic carbon at δ 151.74 for 3f. The main diagnostic FT-IR, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR signals for compounds 3a–f are summarized in Table 1.

ADME prediction

Analysis of ADME-related properties showed that the synthesized series had acceptable molecular weight and hydrogen-bonding values, supporting basic drug-likeness. However, all compounds showed elevated lipophilic-

ity, with QPlogPo/w values above the preferred limit and higher than that of erlotinib, suggesting possible solubility problems and a risk of nonspecific binding. Molecular flexibility was also at the upper end of the preferred range, with 3c–f showing 11 rotatable bonds. Despite this, predicted human oral absorption was high for all compounds. Among the physicochemical descriptors, 3c had the highest PSA value (120.47 Å²), indicating greater polarity that may reduce permeability. Most compounds slightly exceeded the preferred molecular volume of 1500 Å³, whereas 3e was the only analog within this range (1458.98 Å³), and showed the highest globularity value (0.84), suggesting a more compact shape. Overall, Table 2 indicated that 3e had the most balanced size-polarity profile among the synthesized derivatives.

Clear differences were observed in permeability and distribution parameters. Compounds 3e and 3f showed the best predicted QPPCaco/QPPMDCK values of 2261.14/1194.91 and 2476.48/1318.38 nm/s, respectively. In contrast, 3c showed the weakest permeability profile (179.59/77.33 nm/s), which was consistent with its higher PSA value. Compound 3d also remained below the preferred limit. BBB penetration was limited across the whole series, with QPlogBB values ranging from -2.41 to -0.73, suggesting low predicted CNS exposure. Protein-binding values were acceptable for 3d–f (QPlogKhsa 1.26–1.42), whereas those for 3a–c were slightly above the preferred range. The number of predicted metabolic reactions was moderate for all

Table 1. Diagnostic FT-IR, ¹H NMR, and ¹³C NMR signals for compounds 3a–f.

Compound	FT-IR N-H/O-H (cm ⁻¹)	FT-IR C = N/C = O region (cm ⁻¹)	FT-IR substituent band (cm ⁻¹)	¹ H NMR HC = N (ppm)	¹ H NMR CONH (ppm)	Key ¹ H NMR substituent signal	¹³ C NMR C = N / C = O (ppm)	Key ¹³ C NMR substituent signal
3a	3168 (hydrazide N-H)	1631	–	8.66 (s, 1H)	11.88 (s, 1H)	–	163.15 (C = N), 162.67 (C = O)	–
3b	3388–3217 (hydrazide N-H)	1634	600 (Ar-Cl)	8.37 (s, 1H)	11.53 (s, 1H)	–	163.52 (C = N/C = O)	–
3c	3392–3217 (hydrazide N-H)	1652	1513 (NO ₂ bending)	8.48 (s, 1H)	11.80 (s, 1H)	–	163.90 (C = N/C = O)	147.97 (C-NO ₂)
3d	3478 (phenolic O-H), 3378–3245 (hydrazide N-H)	1634	–	8.32 (s, 1H)	11.30 (s, 1H)	9.89 (s, 1H, Ar-OH)	163.36 (C = N/C = O)	157.24 (C-OH)
3e	3201, 3175 (hydrazide N-H)	1631	–	8.42 (s, 1H)	11.73 (s, 1H)	3.81 (s, 3H, p-OCH ₃)	161.66 (C = N), 161.29 (C = O)	162.70 (benzyl-C-OCH ₃)
3f	3468, 3332, 3199 (hydrazide N-H region)	1597–1563 (broad)	1485–1363 [N(CH ₃) ₂ bending]	8.26 (s, 1H)	11.17 (s, 1H)	2.95 (s, 6H, N(CH ₃) ₂)	163.17 (C = N/C = O)	151.74 [Ar-N(CH ₃) ₂]

Table 2. Drug-likeness and physicochemical parameters.

Parameter	Accepted range	3a	3b	3c	3d	3e	3f	Erlotinib
M.W	≤500 g/mol	449.55	484.00	494.55	465.55	479.58	492.62	393.40
HBDs	≤5	1.00	1.00	1.00	2.00	1.00	1.00	1.50
HBAs	≤10	3.75	3.75	4.75	4.50	4.50	4.75	7.40
QPlogPo/w	≤5	7.16	7.66	6.70	6.35	6.52	6.91	3.67
Rotatable bonds	≤10	10.00	10.00	11.00	11.00	11.00	11.00	11.00
Human oral absorption	–	High						
Mol volume	<1500 Å ³	1515.62	1559.77	1604.20	1538.68	1458.98	1537.59	1316.85
PSA	<140 Å ²	76.34	76.35	120.47	98.89	81.11	76.67	63.30
Dipole moment	<10 Debye	5.85	4.99	6.31	6.40	5.09	4.95	5.63
Globularity	Closer to 1	0.75	0.74	0.73	0.75	0.84	0.82	0.77

synthesized compounds (3–4 reactions) compared with erlotinib (6 reactions) (Chirila et al. 2025; Elsaman et al. 2025).

Overall, the series showed high predicted oral absorption, but elevated lipophilicity suggested a potential solubility risk. Compounds 3e (most balanced) and 3f (highest permeability) were prioritized for further optimization.

Molecular docking and MM-GBSA results

The docking study included three known EGFR inhibitors (erlotinib, gefitinib, and lapatinib) and five DUD-E decoys in addition to the synthesized compounds 3a–f (Todsaporn et al. 2023). Native-ligand redocking of the co-crystallized ligand in 1M17 and 4HJO showed good reproduction of the experimental binding mode, with RMSD values of 1.25 Å and 2.59 Å, respectively. In both receptor models, the decoys showed weaker XP and IFD results, and, importantly, none of them formed interactions with the key hinge residue MET769. In contrast, all reference inhibitors and all synthesized compounds retained MET769 interactions, supporting the importance of this residue in the present docking setup.

In receptor 4HJO, the reference inhibitors showed XP scores from –8.53 to –9.20, IFD scores from –11648.57 to

–11716.27, and ΔG_{bind} values from –35.95 to –52.84 kcal/mol. The decoys were clearly weaker, with XP scores of –4.01 to –5.91, IFD scores of –8577.41 to –9677.27, and no MET769 interaction. Among the synthesized series, compounds 3d, 3e, and 3f showed the best overall results (Table 4). Compound 3d gave the best XP score (–9.57) and IFD score (–11755.16), both more favorable than those of the three reference inhibitors. Compound 3f also performed better than the reference inhibitors at the docking stage (XP = –9.35; IFD = –11732.90) and showed the most favorable ΔG_{bind} value in 4HJO (–77.75 kcal/mol). Compound 3e remained highly competitive with the reference inhibitors (XP = –9.21; IFD = –11724.57; ΔG_{bind} = –67.63 kcal/mol). Compound 3c also showed a favorable ΔG_{bind} value (–69.12 kcal/mol), while 3b showed intermediate results and 3a was the weakest ligand in this receptor. All compounds maintained hinge interactions at MET769, supported by additional contacts with residues such as CYS773, LYS721, THR766, ARG817, and THR830, as shown in Fig. 2.

A similar trend was observed in receptor 1M17. The reference inhibitors showed XP scores from –6.44 to –6.92, IFD scores from –12646.95 to –12851.35, and ΔG_{bind} values from –47.27 to –48.94 kcal/mol. Again, the decoys showed weaker results, with XP scores of –4.52 to

Table 3. Predicted permeability, distribution, binding, and metabolism parameters.

Parameter	Acceptable range	3a	3b	3c	3d	3e	3f	Erlotinib
QPPCaco	>500	1118.69	1119.87	179.59	341.49	2261.14	2476.48	4528.97
QPPMDCK	>500	558.47	1378.49	77.33	154.88	1194.91	1318.38	2531.67
QPlogBB	-3.0 to 1.2	-1.23	-1.07	-2.41	-1.95	-0.74	-0.73	-0.51
QPlogKhsa	-1.5 to 1.5	1.60	1.72	1.58	1.36	1.26	1.42	0.24
No. of metabolic reactions	1 to 8	3	3	4	4	4	4	6

Table 4. Molecular docking and MM-GBSA results for receptor 4HJO.

Ligand	XP score	IFD score	dG bind	Protein interactions
Compound 3a	-8.21	-11627.51	-20.24	MET769 - CYS773
Compound 3b	-8.88	-11687.69	-59.07	MET769 - LYS704 - LYS692 - PRO770
Compound 3c	-8.88	-11694.67	-69.12	MET769 - LYS721 - THR830 - PHE699 - LYS704 - water bridge with THR766
Compound 3d	-9.57	-11755.16	-67.02	MET769 - LYS721 - PRO770
Compound 3e	-9.21	-11724.57	-67.63	MET769 - LYS704
Compound 3f	-9.35	-11732.90	-77.75	LYS704 - MET769 - LYS692
Reference (Erlotinib)	-8.53	-11648.57	-35.95	MET769 - CYS773- LYS704 - water bridge with THR766 and THR830
Reference (Gefitinib)	-9.16	-11698.08	-39.46	MET769 - ARG817 - LEU764 - water bridge with THR830
Reference (Lapatinib)	-9.20	-11716.27	-52.84	MET769 - LYS721 - water bridge with THR830 and THR766
ZINC00962181	-5.69	-9583.55	-33.56	LYS692 - LEU694
ZINC20288907	-5.91	-9473.43	-46.49	LYS721
ZINC57256227	-5.68	-9382.65	-32.37	LYS692 - LYS704 - PRO770 - PHE771
ZINC59293222	-5.58	-9677.27	-32.43	LYS692 - LYS704
ZINC66201673	-4.01	-8577.41	-26.02	-

-5.81, IFD scores of -10442.17 to -11638.25, and ΔG_{bind} values of -27.82 to -36.23 kcal/mol, together with the absence of MET769 interaction. Within the synthesized series, compound 3d again showed the strongest profile, with the best XP score (-7.18), IFD score (-12912.62), and ΔG_{bind} value (-72.54 kcal/mol), all more favorable than those of erlotinib, gefitinib, and lapatinib. Compound 3f also performed better than the three reference inhibitors (XP = -7.00; IFD = -12889.27; ΔG_{bind} = -61.23 kcal/mol), while compound 3e showed favorable IFD and MM-GBSA values (-12872.85 and -62.48 kcal/mol). Compounds 3a and 3c showed moderate results, whereas 3b was the weakest ligand in 1M17 (Table 5). As in 4HJO, the interaction pattern of the active compounds was centered on MET769 and supported by additional contacts with residues such as CYS773, LYS721, THR766, and THR830, as shown in Fig. 3.

Overall, the added control set improved the interpretation of the docking study. The poor performance of the DUD-E decoys, together with their lack of MET769 interaction, supported the ability of the workflow to distinguish suitable EGFR-like binding modes from weaker ones. Direct comparison with erlotinib, gefitinib, and lapatinib showed that compounds 3d-f were the most promising members of the series, with 3d showing the best overall profile in 1M17 and 3f giving the most favorable ΔG_{bind} value in 4HJO. These results support the use of docking and MM-GBSA as relative *in silico* tools for prioritizing compounds in this series.

Molecular dynamics results

Docking/IFD poses were evaluated using 200 ns MD simulations of the top ligands 3d (OH) and 3f[N(CH₃)₂] in both EGFR conformations (4HJO inactive-like; 1M17 active-like) (Amelia et al. 2022). No major loss of secondary-structure content was observed during the trajectories, with mean SSE values of 47.16% (4HJO-3d), 45.76% (1M17-3d), 47.33% (4HJO-3f), and 45.07% (1M17-3f) (Suppl. material 1: fig. S1). Protein RMSD plateaued at ~2.0-2.6 Å (4HJO-3d), ~2.2-2.8 Å (1M17-3d), ~2.2-3.0 Å (4HJO-3f), and a stable ~4.3-4.6 Å (1M17-3f) without SSE loss. Ligand RMSD (protein-fit) stabilized at ~3.0 Å and spiked to ~5.2 Å (4HJO-3d), ~5.0-6.5 Å (4HJO-3f), ~3.0-4.0 Å (1M17-3d), and ~2.5-3.2 Å (1M17-3f), as shown in Suppl. material 1: fig. S2. RMSF peaks were limited to loops/termini (~4.6-5.5 Å), core regions (~0.6-1.2 Å), and ligand medians (~1.0-1.2 Å), as shown in Suppl. material 1: fig. S3 (Bouzina et al. 2023). Ligand-protein interactions for each complex were as follows: in 4HJO-3d, MET769 hydrophobic interaction was ~84%, LYS721 H-bond was ~64%, π -cation interaction was ~65%, and the LEU694-proximal water bridge was ~41%. In 1M17-3d, THR766's H-bond was ~92%, MET769's H-bond was ~93%, LYS721's H-bond/water bridge was ~96%, and ASP776 (~134% aggregated) and CYS773 (~49%) were often water bridged. In 4HJO-3f, MET769's H-bond was ~76%, PHE711's H-bond/hydrophobic interaction was ~99%, PRO770's water bridge was ~67%, and ALA719

Figure 2. A. Compound 3a; B. Compound 3b; C. Compound 3c; D. Compound 3d; E. Compound 3e; F. Compound 3f; G. Erlotinib; H. Gefitinib; I. Lapatinib docked into the active site of receptor 4HJO, showing 3D and 2D poses.

Table 5. Molecular docking and MM-GBSA results for receptor 1M17.

Ligand	XP score	IFD score	dG bind	Protein interactions
Compound 3a	-6.55	-12863.37	-39.49	MET769 - CYS773
Compound 3b	-6.20	-12726.13	-40.50	MET769 - CYS773 - THR766 - ALA719
Compound 3c	-6.31	-12756.80	-47.65	MET769 - LYS704 - THR766
Compound 3d	-7.18	-12912.62	-72.54	MET769 - CYS773 - LYS721 - THR766
Compound 3e	-6.67	-12872.85	-62.48	MET769 - THR830 - LYS721 - water bridge with THR766
Compound 3f	-7.00	-12889.27	-61.23	MET769 - THR830 - THR766
Reference (Erlotinib)	-6.44	-12851.35	-48.94	MET769 - CYS773 - water bridge with THR766 and THR830
Reference (Gefitinib)	-6.46	-12646.95	-48.03	MET769 - LEU764 - ASP831
Reference (Lapatinib)	-6.92	-12649.61	-47.27	MET769 - LYS721 - ASP831 - GLY833 - water bridge with THR766 and GLN767
ZINC00962181	-4.87	-10642.04	-27.82	LYS721 - ASP831 - ASN818
ZINC20288907	-5.81	-11638.25	-31.96	ARG779 - CYS773
ZINC57256227	-4.52	-10442.17	-30.60	PHE699 - ARG817 - ASP831 - water bridge with THR766
ZINC59293222	-4.66	-10540.16	-36.23	ASP831 - CYS773
ZINC66201673	-4.88	-10537.21	-35.07	CYS773

Figure 3. A. Compound 3a; B. Compound 3b; C. Compound 3c; D. Compound 3d; E. Compound 3e; F. Compound 3f; G. Erlotinib; H. Gefitinib; I. Lapatinib docked into the active site of receptor 1M17, showing 3D and 2D poses.

and LEU694 were both ~55% hydrophobic. In 1M17-3f, THR830 H-bond was ~99%, MET769 H-bond was ~66%, PHE699 hydrophobic interaction was ~90%, ALA719 was ~75%, and water bridges near THR766 were ~36% (Suppl. material 1: fig. S4). Both ligands maintained recurrent ATP-site contacts during the 200 ns simulation duration, but 3d was more rigid/less mobile, and 3f had THR830 occupancy and wider water-mediated stabilization (Todsaporn et al. 2023; Yang et al. 2023). However, these trajectories were interpreted cautiously, since slower dissociation events or alternative long-timescale behaviors cannot be excluded beyond the simulated window. Moreover, RMSD/RMSF and interaction-occupancy results describe pose behavior within this window only and do not by themselves prove binding affinity, residence time, or inhibitory activity.

Conclusion

A series of benzohydrazide derivatives (3a–f) was synthesized and characterized using FT-IR, ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR. *In silico* ADME predicted high oral absorption; however, consistently high lipophilicity suggests potential solubility liabilities that require optimization, while compound 3e showed the most balanced overall profile. Evaluating the derivatives against two EGFR kinase conformations (PDB: 1M17 and 4HJO) suggested conformation-dependent recognition in the modeled EGFR pockets. Prime MM-GBSA analysis indicated that compound 3d had the strongest MM-GBSA estimate in the active-like EGFR state ($\Delta G_{\text{bind}} = -72.54$ kcal/mol for 1M17), while compound 3f had the strongest MM-GBSA estimate in the inactive-like state ($\Delta G_{\text{bind}} = -77.75$ kcal/mol for

4HJO), both compared with the EGFR reference inhibitors. Molecular dynamics simulations of the top-ranked ligands within the ATP-binding pocket maintained recurrent ATP-site contacts during the simulation duration. Because no biological assays were performed, the docking/MM-GBSA and MD findings should be interpreted as relative *in silico* indicators rather than confirmed inhibitory activity. These findings suggest that the synthesized benzohydrazide scaffold is promising for EGFR-directed

optimization, with compounds 3d and 3f prioritized for experimental validation and compound 3e retained as a useful ADME-balanced analog.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Author contributions

Mohammed R. Abdulmonem: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data collection, Writing – original draft. Monther F. Mahdi and Ayad M. R. Raauf: Methodology, Validation, Writing – review and editing. All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

Supplementary material 1

Molecular dynamics analysis for EGFR-ligand complexes

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Data type: docx

Explanation note: Suppl. material 1 contains additional molecular dynamics analyses for the top-ranked compounds 3d and 3f in complex with EGFR (PDB: 4HJO and 1M17), including protein secondary structure stability (fig. S1), ligand and protein RMSD (fig. S2), ligand and protein RMSF (fig. S3), and ligand-protein interaction profiles (fig. S4).

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